

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

Check it out WP2 update (June 2021) - Status of EdiCitnet database & advancements regarding the tools

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

WP2 team has shared several good news such as:

- The submission of second article of WP2 entitled “Tools for edible cities: A review of tools for planning and assessing edible nature-based solutions”.
- The increased collaboration between WP1,2,6 and 7 for the integration of the project network marketplace, and toolbox.
- EdiCitNet DATABASE has more than 20 different countries and more than 100 cities. These cities and countries are represented on the form of more the 300 PROFILES.
- The SEARCH TOOL brings the possibility of searching for interactive and non-interactive profiles and by location.
- A new version of the PERFORMANCE ASSESMENT TOOL brings two novelties. User can explore, compare and check out the top 10 Edible City Solutions per typology (e.g. community gardens) in terms of sustainability, urban challenges and ecosystem services.
- The EDIBLE CITY GAME. The urban model of SFL is built, tested and calibrated by SFL’s practitioners that are playing in single-player modality. Practioners have showed a great interest in the functionalities of the serious game.
- DESIGN AND PLANNING TOOL. The "Individual level" and "City level" options were replaced by, respectively, "Create your own ECS" and "Create a city plan of ECS". The former option is intended for individual users, to discover resources requirements and expected yield. The latter is to be used by city planners, to investigate the impact of ECS on city's food production, resources management and sustainability. "Create your own ECS" option is almost fully operational. We decided to remove the map on the entering page so that the user will only have to provide the plot area size and will not have to draw polygons (to be implemented very soon). "Create a city plan of ECS" option currently allows for the user to draw polygons or areas, corresponding to neighbourhoods, city districts, etc. which they want to analyse. For these areas, land uses are automatically generated based on the Urban Atlas.

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

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Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

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Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

03/06/2021

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Joana Castellar

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

ICRA

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Postdoc

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

barcelona, Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jcastellar@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
- No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
- No, none of them
- Only on Twitter
- Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

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